

Comparison of the Effectiveness of Lectures versus Small Group Discussion versus Self-Directed Learning among MBBS Students: A Quasi Experimental Study

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Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: We have undertaken this study to compare the effectiveness and perception of students for lectures, small group discussions, and self-directed learning among second year MBBS students.

Methods: A total of 141 students were included in this study. For finding the effectiveness of each learning method 10 marks MCQ test was taken and questionnaires were given to find the perception of students for learning methods.

Results: Among 141 participants the mean scores for the lecture was 5.9, small group discussion (SGD) was 9, and self-directed learning (SDL) was 6.5 out of 10. The mean scores of small group discussions were higher and statistically significant. Maximum marks in lectures, small group discussions and self-directed learning were 9, 10, 10. Although 10 marks was scored by both small group discussion and self-directed learning group, there is a significant difference between the percentage of students scoring 10 marks in SGD (41.8%) and SDL (2.1%) stating that SGD is more effective. Perception of students was better for small group discussions when compared to lectures and self-directed learning.

Conclusion: After a thorough literature review, ours is the only study that compared lectures, small group discussions and self-directed learning. Students performed better and they preferred small group discussions over the other teaching method because it was more interactive, involved smaller groups, and encouraged their active participation.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Medical Undergraduates, Perception, Teaching methods.

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Introduction

The objective of undergraduate medical education is to train medical graduates with the necessary knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values to function appropriately and effectively as future doctors. To achieve this National Medical Council of India has used different teaching methods like lectures, small group discussions, self-directed learning, seminars, bedside teaching, role plays and practical sessions. [1] Among different teaching methods lectures are the most commonly employed, here large group of students receive more information in a short time. Lectures have the disadvantage of having no interactions, short attention span, and lesser retention of the topics taught. [2,3] Small group discussion is a learning method involving a small number of students, involves interactions and can overcome the disadvantages of lectures. However, it requires more teachers and infrastructure. [1,3] Self-directed learning is a learning method where students take initiative and responsibility for their

own learning which can improve critical thinking, problem-solving, and creativity in students. [1,4] As these teaching-learning methods have their own advantages and disadvantages it is important to know which is more effective and which method students prefer. So, here we have undertaken a study to compare the effectiveness and perception of students for lectures, small group discussions, and self-directed learning.

Materials and Methods

A Quasi-experimental study, single group post-test was undertaken among second-year MBBS students at the department of Pharmacology, Belagavi Institute of Medical Sciences Belagavi, India. Prior clearance from the Institutional Ethical Committee was taken (BIMS-IEC/260/2023-24). A total of 141 students who were willing to participate were included in the study after their consent. All the

study participants were included in all the three teaching-learning methods and test was taken after each learning method as described below.

Finding the Effectiveness of Lectures: A lecture class on anti-viral drugs was conducted a day before and 10 marks MCQ test was given to all the students.

Finding the Effectiveness of self-directed learning: For self-directed learning, students were given a topic laxative and purgative a day prior, where the students took the initiative and responsibility to study on their own. Students were free to select their own learning resources and strategies to acquire the knowledge. 10 marks MCQ test was taken for all the students.

Finding the Effectiveness of Small Group Discussion: Anthelmintics was chosen for small group discussion and students were informed prior to the study. 141 students were divided into 5 small groups and pharmacology faculties conducted the small group discussions. It was a 2-way interaction conducted for about 45 minutes. Students were encouraged to actively participate by sharing their thoughts, asking questions. Following the small group discussion 10 marks MCQ test was taken.

Finding the perception of students for lectures, small group discussions, and self-directed learning: The questionnaire was given and students were asked to tick one of the learning methods based on the questionnaire.

Statistical Analysis: The data collected was compiled in Microsoft Excel. Descriptive statistics was used to present the data. Collected data was expressed as percentages and graphs. Friedman non-parametric test was used to evaluate the statistical significance and SPSS software version 25 was used for the same. P-value < 0.005 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Among 141 participants the mean scores for the lecture were 5.9, for the small group discussion they were 9, and for the self-directed learning were 6.5 out of 10. The differences among the mean were statistically significant, where the p-value is < 0.0001

None of the study participants scored 0 marks in any of the learning methods. Minimum marks scored in lecture, SGD, and SDL were 2, 6, 2, respectively, while maximum marks in lecture, SGD, and SDL were 9, 10, 10.

Although the maximum mark in SGD and SDL was 10, the percentage of students scoring 10 in SGD was 41.8%, while in SDL it was only 2.1%, and none scored 10 marks in the lecture. [Table 1] In SGD, minimum marks were considerably greater than in Lecture and SDL. In the SGD group, the maximum percentage of students (41.8%) scored 10. Whereas in lecture and SDL, the maximum percentage of students (27.7%) have scored 6. [Figure 1]

Table 1: Comparison of marks obtained in different learning methods

Learning method	No. of participants	Mean	Minimum marks scored (% of students)	Maximum marks scored (% of students)
Lecture	141	5.9	2 (2.8%)	9 (6.4%)
SGD	141	9	6 (2.8%)	10 (41.8%)
SDL	141	6.5	2 (1.8%)	10 (2.1%)

Figure 1: Depicts the percentage of students scoring different marks in different learning methods

Student's perceptions regarding different learning methods are shown in Table 2.

In most instances, the majority of students preferred SGD over lecture and SDL for learning. Most of the students have given the opinion that SGD was better for creating interest, motivation, improving interactions, and retaining the subject. However,

SDL motivated students more to use additional learning sources when compared to the other two.

Nearly half of the students felt that non-essential topics for exams were taught in lectures. Overall 62.4% of students preferred SGD, 22% preferred SDL and 15.6% preferred lecture. [Table 2]

Table 2: Results showing students perception using questionnaire

S.No	Questions	Lecture (%)	SGD (%)	SDL (%)
1.	Which learning method motivates for learning	17.7	66.7	15.6
2.	Which learning method creates interest	17.7	65.2	17
3.	Which learning method is better for understanding the learning objective	31.9	56	12.1
4.	Which learning method facilitated interactive teaching	9.9	83.7	6.4
5.	In which learning method environment was more relaxed	29.8	37.6	32.6
6.	In which learning method subject was in-depth	39	40.4	20.6
7.	In which learning method information was retained better	10.6	70.2	19.1
8.	Which learning method motivates to use additional learning resources	17.7	40.4	41.8
9.	In which learning method topics which are not essential for exams were taught	42.6	28.4	29.1
10.	Overall which learning method do you prefer	15.6	62.4	22

Discussion

In our study we involved the learners to find out their perspective about effective delivery of teaching modules, so as to know an inclusive teaching and learning environment.

Students preferred small group discussion as it involved an effective communication between the teachers and students, relaxed learning environment,

interesting and informative learning process. A study conducted by Padugupati et.al showed similar results stating SGD is better than lecture. They have compared the pre-test, post-test of lecture and SGD in which scores of SGD were statistically significant. [5] Similar studies by Hameed S et.al, Naveena et.al, Roshini et.al showed that they actively contributed their invaluable inputs. In group discussion students outperformed then the didactic

lectures. [6-8] There are no studies that have compared the effectiveness of SDL with any other teaching learning methods. Studies conducted by Bhandari et.al, and Somdatta Patra et.al concluded that students were satisfied with SDL. It showed that it improved their understanding and was an innovative way of learning with extensive literature review. [9,10] In our study also some of the students preferred SDL because they had freedom to choose the learning resources, had relaxed learning environment as they could choose their own time and place of study.

Conclusion

To conclude, the main goal of our study was to compare learning methods lectures, small group discussions, and self-directed learning. Students' perception was more favorable towards small group discussion over the other learning methods. Students actively participated in the small group discussion as they were more comfortable expressing their ideas in an intimate group, it helped them to improve their communication skills and also provided a supportive environment. Thus, a greater number of small group discussions should be encouraged in the MBBS curriculum to enhance the knowledge and skills of undergraduate students.

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